

Modelling of the Initial Core of the LDR Lite Benchmark within the EU-funded EASI-SMR Project

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ABSTRACT

Core physics studies related to soluble boron free light water SMR cores are currently being carried out within the EU-funded EASI-SMR project. Two designs are considered: PRATIC, an academic pressurized SMR benchmark developed by CEA and LDR lite, a benchmark version of the LDR-50 district heating reactor. During the project steady state, depletion and transient modelling are investigated using computational tools at different fidelity levels. In this paper the initial core of the LDR lite is modelled at beginning of cycle conditions. Two neutronics only states and a hot full power state with neutronics-thermal hydraulics coupling are studied. Reference results calculated with the Monte Carlo code Serpent and the coupled code system Serpent-SUBCHANLOW are compared against nodal diffusion based results calculated with Ants/Ants-SUBCHANFLOW and DYN3D.

Keywords: Ants, DYN3D, Serpent, LDR

1. INTRODUCTION

EASI-SMR (Ensuring Assessment of Safety Innovation for SMR) is an ongoing project funded by the European Union with the following key objectives: ensure the highest level of safety of light water SMRs based on passive systems, assess the safety impact of light water SMRs designs' specificities and address regulatory and societal challenges towards the deployment of SMRs in Europe [1, 2]. Work package (WP) seven of the project titled "Advanced Core Physics Studies of Boron-Free SMR-cores" [3] focuses on studying two boron free cores: PRATIC and LDR (Low temperature District heating Reactor) lite. During the project steady state, depletion and transient simulations will be run for both cores using tools at different fidelity levels (diffusion, SP3/SN and Monte Carlo).

This paper covers the current status of the LDR lite simulations or more specifically, the modelling of the initial core at beginning of cycle (BOC) conditions. Two neutronics only states and a hot full power (HFP) state with neutronics-thermal hydraulics (TH) coupling are simulated. Reference results are generated with the Monte Carlo code Serpent [4] and a coupling between Serpent and the subchannel code SUBCHANFLOW (SCF) [5]. Nodal diffusion based results obtained with Ants[6]/Ants-SCF and DYN3D [7] are compared against the reference results.

2. LDR LITE CORE

LDR lite is a public benchmark version of the LDR-50 reactor originally developed at VTT and now commercialized by Steady Energy Oy. This 50 MWth light water reactor has been designed for low temperature heat production applications. The design features in-vessel control rod drives, natural circulation driven primary circuit, self-pressurization and passive decay heat removal through a dual

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vessel design. The core is soluble boron free and long term reactivity control is achieved by using gray control rods and burnable absorbers. The reactor core consists of 37 17x17 square fuel assemblies with an active height of 100 cm.

The core loading pattern for the initial core of LDR lite is shown on the left side of Figure 1. The fuel is low enriched UO_2 and there are six different assembly types in the initial core. Four of them contain gadolinium. In the radial direction the fuel assemblies are surrounded by a stainless steel reflector. Control rods, which are present in each assembly, have been divided into eight groups with four regulating and four safety groups. The locations of the control rods groups are presented on the right side of Figure 1. The absorbers parts of the control rods consist of Inconel-718 lower section and 90 % enriched boron carbide upper section. The heights of these sections are 60 / 40 cm for the regulating rods and 5 / 95 cm for the safety rods. More detailed description of the LDR lite core is available in the benchmark specifications [8].

Figure 1. Left: Core loading pattern. Right: Control rod group locations. Source of the figures: [8].

3. DESCRIPTION OF THE ANALYSES AT BOC

The simulations for LDR lite in WP7 of the EASI-SMR project started with the modelling of the initial core at BOC. This fresh core benchmarking phase consists of the modelling of two neutronics only states with fixed TH conditions and HFP state with neutronics-TH coupling. The former two are the all-rods-out (ARO) state and a critical state with predefined control rod group positions. These positions have been iterated with a simple algorithm aiming to minimize the radial peaking of the power distribution. The positions are given in Table I. The fixed TH conditions, representative of core average values at nominal power, are listed in Table II. Zero xenon is used in the neutronics only states.

Also in the HFP state predefined control rod positions iterated in a similar manner as in the critical state are used. These positions are given in Table 13 of Ref. [8]. TH boundary conditions given in Table 9 of Ref. [8] are used and fuel behaviour is modelled in a simplified manner by utilizing fixed thermophysical properties given in Table 10 of Ref. [8]. Equilibrium xenon is used in the neutronics solution.

Table I. Positions of control rod groups for the critical state.

Group	Insertion (%)
S1	0
R2	76
R3	86
S4	0
R5	75
R6	72
S7	0
S8	0

Table II. Fixed TH conditions for the neutronics only states.

Property	Value	Unit
Fuel temperature	525	K
Coolant temperature	410	K
Coolant density	0.92915	g/cm ³

4. MODELS

4.1. Group Constant Generation

Group constants for both Ants and DYN3D were generated with Serpent separately for the ARO/critical states and for the HFP state using ENDF/B-VII.1 based cross section library. For the ARO and critical states the group constants were generated directly for the state point given in Table II. For the HFP state variation in the group constants due to variations in the thermal hydraulics conditions were taken into account with 9 branches resulting from combining 3 fuel temperatures (low, nominal, high) with 3 moderator temperatures/densities (low, nominal, high).

Fuel assemblies were homogenized using 2D infinite lattice quarter assembly models with fundamental mode leakage correction applied. One assembly width of radial reflector was homogenized from a 2D full core model into quarter assembly sized regions and the axial reflector was homogenized using a single assembly 3D model. The fuel assemblies utilized Cumulative Migration Method (CMM)[9] based diffusion coefficients and for the reflectors the diffusion coefficients were evaluated based on the out scatter approximation with transport correction applied to ¹H in water. Both Ants and DYN3D used fuel assembly discontinuity factors calculated directly by Serpent.

For Ants the fuel facing discontinuity factors for the reflector nodes were evaluated based on heterogeneous surface fluxes tallied in the Serpent 2D full core simulation and homogeneous surface fluxes which were obtained from single node Ants calculations utilizing group constants and boundary condition currents from the Serpent full core simulation. As an additional step, for each node the reflector discontinuity factor was corrected by the ratio of the fuel side infinite lattice assembly discontinuity factor and the fuel side full core evaluated discontinuity factor as suggested in Ref. [10].

For the first row of the radial reflector at the boundary between the active core and the reflector, the discontinuity factors for DYN3D were calculated as the ratio of heterogeneous to homogeneous surface fluxes. Heterogeneous fluxes were obtained from the Serpent 2D full core simulation, while homogeneous surface fluxes were calculated during post-processing by a separate diffusion solver applying the same nodal expansion as DYN3D and using Serpent full core surface currents of each reflector region as boundary conditions. For the second row of reflector nodes, the discontinuity factors of the neighboring first-row reflector regions were applied.

In Ants, polynomials were used to represent the dependency of the group constants on thermal hydraulics conditions in the HFP state. For the fuel assemblies first and second order terms were used for the square root of the fuel temperature and the moderator density. In addition, a first order cross term was included. The reflector group constants were fitted with first and second order terms for the moderator density.

For DYN3D the group constants are represented in a NEMTAB-like multi-dimensional table library with linear interpolation between branching points in fuel temperature and moderator density.

4.2. Serpent-SCF

The Serpent model was built according to the benchmark specifications. ENDF/B-VII.1 based cross section library was used. When evaluating the effective multiplication factors and power distributions for the ARO and critical states 50 billion active neutron histories were simulated. In the estimation of the control rod group worths 5 billion active neutron histories were simulated in each transport calculation. The same amount of histories was also simulated on each coupled iteration when solving the HFP state. The standard deviation of the effective multiplication factor was less than approximately 1 pcm in all transport calculations.

The reference solution for the HFP state was produced by running a coupled calculation between Serpent and SCF. The coolant flow was solved on a subchannel level and the temperature distribution of each fuel rod separately. It should be noted that severe convergence issues were encountered with the default upwards flow only (UPWA) solution algorithm of SCF and the alternative SOLA algorithm had to be used to be able to model the core at subchannel level.

4.3. Ants-SCF

Axially the Ants model consisted of 20 nodes: 18 in the active core and one in both bottom and top reflectors. Radially the model included the fuel assemblies and one assembly-wide of radial reflector. 2x2 subnodalization was used in each assembly.

For the HFP state a coupled calculation between Ants and SCF was run. The TH solution in SCF was on a quarter assembly level i.e. with one channel/representative fuel rod for each quarter assembly. UPWA algorithm was used in SCF since no convergence issues were encountered with the quarter assembly level resolution.

4.4. DYN3D

DYN3D model applied the same spatial discretization as the Ants model: 20 axial nodes and 2x2 subnodalization for each fuel assembly and assembly-size radial reflector region. The model utilized DYN3D's internal TH solver, representing the core as a set of 1D parallel two-phase flow channels, with a channel assigned to each quarter-assembly.

5. RESULTS

5.1. ARO and Critical State

The effective multiplication factors ($k_{\text{eff};s}$) estimated with Serpent and differences in reactivity compared to Ants and DYN3D are shown in Table III. In both states both nodal codes underestimate the $k_{\text{eff};s}$. The differences are smaller in the critical state which is to be expected since the group constants were leakage corrected to $k_{\text{eff}} = 1.0$. When moving from 2 to 4 groups the differences increase for both codes in both states.

Estimated control rod group worths and differences between the nodal codes and Serpent are presented in Table IV. For DYN3D the absolute difference compared to Serpent is smaller for seven of the eight control rod groups with 4 energy groups compared to 2 energy groups and for Ants for six groups.

Root mean square (RMS) and maximum absolute (MAX) differences between the relative power distributions calculated with the nodal diffusion codes and Serpent are presented in Tables V and VI. The differences have been evaluated based on local relative powers as $(\text{Nodal} - \text{Serpent}) \times 100$. With 2 en-

Table III. Effective multiplication factors estimated with Serpent in the ARO and critical states, and differences in reactivity between Ants/DYN3D and Serpent in pcm.

State	Serpent	Ants		DYN3D	
		2 group	4 groups	2 groups	4 groups
ARO	1.07347	-195	-223	-148	-262
Critical state	1.00275	-83	-162	-8	-235

Table IV. Control rod group worths calculated with Serpent, and differences between Ants/DYN3D and Serpent in pcm.

Group	Serpent	Ants		DYN3D	
		2 groups	4 groups	2 groups	4 groups
All	20826	-114	66	-50	46
S1	1020	1	3	-7	15
R2	2521	-24	-2	-42	25
R3	2354	-14	-6	-13	-1
S4	1390	33	17	48	4
R5	2760	-28	-8	-42	15
R6	3296	56	59	68	57
S7	1640	64	41	85	17
S8	1205	59	45	73	35

ergy groups the differences are in general smaller for Ants compared to DYN3D. Ants 2 groups clearly outperforms Ants 4 groups in all distributions in both states. With DYN3D the use of 4 groups results in smaller differences in assembly powers but larger differences in axial powers compared to 2 groups.

Relative assembly and pin powers in the critical state estimated with 2 energy groups are compared to Serpent reference powers in Figures 2 and 3, respectively. A 45-degree symmetry sector is shown. The distributions of the differences for Ants and DYN3D look quite similar. The largest differences in the pin powers are observed in the assemblies at the perimeter of the active core.

Table V. Differences between the relative power distributions estimated with Ants/DYN3D and Serpent in the ARO state.

Distribution	Ants				DYN3D			
	2 groups		4 groups		2 groups		4 groups	
	RMS	MAX	RMS	MAX	RMS	MAX	RMS	MAX
Axial	0.7	1.7	1.0	2.1	0.7	1.8	1.0	2.1
Assembly	0.4	0.7	0.5	1.0	0.7	1.3	0.4	0.8
Pin	0.7	2.6	0.9	4.2	1.0	6.0	1.0	7.6

5.2. HFP state

Effective multiplication factors calculated for the HFP state are given in Table VII. The differences between Ants and Serpent are clearly smaller compared to the differences between DYN3D and Serpent. As in the neutronics only states, larger differences are obtained with 4 groups compared to 2 groups.

Table VI. Differences between the relative power distributions estimated with Ants/DYN3D and Serpent in the critical state.

Distribution	Ants				DYN3D			
	2 groups		4 groups		2 groups		4 groups	
	RMS	MAX	RMS	MAX	RMS	MAX	RMS	MAX
Axial	1.7	4.1	2.6	6.0	1.7	4.1	2.4	5.6
Assembly	0.8	1.6	0.9	2.1	1.1	1.9	0.8	1.8
Pin	1.2	3.9	1.5	5.9	1.5	6.6	1.4	8.0

Figure 2. Comparison of relative assembly powers in the critical state with 2 energy groups in Ants and DYN3D.

Figure 3. Comparison of relative pin powers in the critical state with 2 energy groups in Ants and DYN3D.

Differences in the power distributions are shown in Table VIII. With Ants smaller differences are obtained for the assembly and pin power distributions compared to DYN3D. Differences in the axial power distribution are smaller for DYN3D. Assembly and pin power distributions estimated with 2 groups are compared against Serpent reference values in Figures 4 and 5, respectively.

It should be noted that the HFP results are affected by the differences in the TH solutions. In Serpent-SCF the solution is on a subchannel/pin-by-pin level, while in Ants-SCF and DYN3D the solution is on a quarter assembly level. In addition, in the TH solver of DYN3D the channels are isolated, while in the SCF models the channels exchange mass and energy.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper the current status of the modelling of the LDR lite core within the EASI-SMR project was described. Results calculated with Serpent(-SCF), Ants(-SCF) and DYN3D for the initial core at BOC conditions were shown and observed differences were briefly discussed. Increasing the number of energy groups from 2 to 4 increased the differences compared to Serpent when looking at the effective

Table VII. Effective multiplication factor estimated with Serpent in the HFP state, and differences in reactivity between Ants/DYN3D and Serpent in pcm.

Serpent	Ants		DYN3D	
	2 group	4 groups	2 groups	4 groups
1.00154	2	-67	-206	-412

Table VIII. Differences between the relative power distributions estimated with Ants/DYN3D and Serpent in the HFP state.

Distribution	Ants				DYN3D			
	2 groups		4 groups		2 groups		4 groups	
	RMS	MAX	RMS	MAX	RMS	MAX	RMS	MAX
Axial	1.8	3.7	2.5	5.4	0.6	1.7	0.9	3.0
Assembly	0.7	1.1	0.7	1.5	1.2	2.0	0.8	1.7
Pin	1.0	3.5	1.2	5.1	1.6	6.0	1.5	6.8

Figure 4. Comparison of relative assembly powers in the HFP state with 2 energy groups in Ants and DYN3D.

Figure 5. Comparison of relative pin powers in the HFP state with 2 energy groups in Ants and DYN3D.

multiplication factors. Control rod group worths were estimated better with 4 groups. Ants 4 groups had clearly worse performance in terms of estimating the power distributions compared to 2 groups. With DYN3D such a clear conclusion could not be made and for example assembly power distributions were estimated better with 4 groups. In the HFP state the differences between Ants and DYN3D results were larger compared to the neutronics only states. In 2026 the modelling of LDR lite will continue with transient and depletion calculations.

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